

From Trajectories to Decisions: Reconstructing Pedestrian Crossing Scenarios to Reveal Behavior under Risk

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Abstract. Pedestrian crossing behavior emerges from complex interactions between spatial geometry, traffic dynamics, and individual risk perception. This study integrates high-resolution trajectory analysis with scenario reconstruction and controlled experimentation to investigate how pedestrians perceive and respond to risk at urban intersections. Trajectory data were collected at two contrasting intersections near a university campus in Munich. Data were analyzed to identify kinematic states, interaction patterns, and risk levels using Time-to-Collision (TTC) and Post-Encroachment Time (PET) metrics. Selected real-world crossing events were reconstructed in Unreal Engine 5 to create immersive experimental environments, with geographic context established using real-world data, preserving authentic spatial-temporal traffic pressure. A controlled user study is in development to correlate subjective risk perception and individual characteristics with observed crossing strategies. The framework demonstrates how trajectory datasets can be transformed into experimental infrastructures that bridge real-world spatial measurement and behavioural investigation of decision-making under risk.

Submission Type. Analysis.

BoK Concepts. [AM13] Representation transformation, [GD2] Data Collection, [AM7] Spatial statistics

Keywords. Trajectory data, intersection, behavioral study, traffic psychology

1 Introduction

Pedestrian crossing is a fundamental yet complex activity in urban mobility. Although pedestrian behaviour has been widely studied, many approaches rely on aggregated safety indicators, observations, or simplified simulations (Jiang et al., 2025; Maruhn, 2021). These methods often provide limited insight into how pedestrians dynamically adjust their movement in response to surrounding geometry and traffic flow, and crucially, how they perceive and respond to risk during crossing.

High-resolution roadside sensing now enables the capture of trajectories as continuous spatio-temporal processes, revealing subtle behaviours such as hesitation, dynamic repositioning, and interaction-driven adjustments. However, movement patterns alone cannot fully explain the decision mechanisms behind these adaptations. Observed trajectories describe what pedestrians do, but they do not reveal how pedestrians interpret and respond to the risks posed by the roadway. This study therefore pursues three objectives: (1) to characterise pedestrian crossing behaviour and risk exposure at two geometrically contrasting intersections using high-resolution trajectory data; (2) to reconstruct representative high-risk crossing scenarios in a simulation environment; and (3) to investigate the relationship between objective risk indicators, subjective risk perception, and individual crossing decisions through a controlled user study. This integrated approach bridges the gap between descriptive spatial observation and the underlying mechanisms of human decision-making under risk.

2 Data and Methods

The empirical foundation of this study is a high-resolution trajectory dataset collected at two adjacent intersections near a university campus in Munich. The sites were selected based on their contrasting spatial configurations: a signalized four-leg intersection with clear pedestrian demarcations (A) and an unsignalized T-intersection where crossing is informal (B). This choice allows for a controlled comparison of behaviour within differing "geometries of risk." Data were captured via a roadside sensing platform at a temporal resolution of 0.1 seconds, recording high-resolution 3D coordinates of pedestrians, cyclists, and vehicles.

Figure 1. Study area and data collection site (A and B).

The raw trajectories were enhanced through noise filtering, smoothing, and reconnection of fragmented segments. Each pedestrian crossing was normalised from curb departure to curb arrival to emphasise the structure of the crossing process rather than absolute duration. Crossing behaviour was decomposed into kinematic states derived from instantaneous velocity components, distinguishing crossing, standing or yielding, and lateral repositioning. To identify representative interaction scenarios, risk levels were classified using spatial-temporal proximity metrics, including Time-to-Collision (TTC) and Post-Encroachment Time (PET) (Ghadirzadeh et al., 2022).

Selected real-world crossing events were reconstructed in Unreal Engine 5. Geographic context was established using the Cesium plugin, integrating OpenStreetMap 3D buildings and aerial imagery to ensure spatial fidelity. Dynamic traffic participants were driven by the original recorded trajectories to preserve authentic spatial-temporal pressure. The accuracy of the reconstruction was verified through a visual consistency check against the ground-truth LiDAR point cloud data.

Figure 2. 3D environment and traffic simulation in Unreal Engine 5

A controlled user study is being developed within the reconstructed environment. Participants will perform pedestrian crossing decisions in multiple scenarios representing low-, medium-, and high-risk situations. Behavioural responses such as hesitation, gap acceptance, and crossing timing will be recorded. Questionnaires will capture subjective risk perception and individual characteristics to support interpretation of decision differences. This experimental component is currently in preparation and its results will be reported in future work.

2.1 Data and Software Availability

Relevant data and analysis code are not publicly available at this stage. They will be made available upon completion of the study via an open repository in accordance with the AGILE Reproducible Paper Guidelines.

3 Results

The trajectory analysis reveals clear behavioural divergence between the two intersections. Continuous crossing is more prevalent at the signalized intersection, while cautious and adaptive strategies occur more frequently at the unsignalized site. Pedestrians at the unsignalized intersection hesitate and reposition within the roadway more often, indicating ongoing reassessment of traffic conditions rather than a single commitment to crossing.

Risk-based interaction analysis demonstrates that high-risk encounters occur more frequently at the unsignalized site. Pedestrian responses differ by interacting road user type: interactions with motor vehicles are associated with more conservative behaviour, while cyclist interactions more often coincide with continued or adaptive crossing. Pedestrians also tend to continue crossing under higher risk primarily when they are already close to completing the crossing, suggesting dynamic adjustment of safety thresholds based on spatial progress.

A pilot implementation in Unreal Engine 5 demonstrated that high-risk interactive events can be successfully replayed within a geospatially accurate 3D environment. Building on this, a controlled user study investigating pedestrian risk perception is currently in development. By performing crossing decisions within the reconstructed scenarios, participants' subjective risk perception and individual characteristics can be correlated with the kinematic adaptations identified in the trajectory analysis. These results will be presented in future work.

4 Conclusion

This study demonstrates how trajectory analysis and scenario reconstruction can extend the analytical value of high-resolution movement data beyond descriptive observation. By transforming recorded trajectories into immersive experimental environments, the framework bridges real-world measurement and controlled behavioural investigation of decision-making under risk. Movement trajectories are thus repositioned not only as observational records but as active foundations for understanding how humans navigate uncertainty in urban space.

The approach illustrates how spatial trajectory datasets can be converted into experimental infrastructures that preserve real-world complexity while enabling repeatable analysis. Linking trajectory analytics with immersive reconstruction supports evidence-based safety assessment and human-centered intersection design. In this sense, the study outlines a pathway toward deeper integration between spatial sensing, behavioural experimentation, and urban mobility research.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing, grammar checking, and sentence structure.

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